

Synthetic, spectral and antimicrobial activity studies of first row transition metal complexes derived from lansoprazole drug

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Abstract : Transition metal complexes of ZrO^{II} , VO^{II} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} have been synthesized with lansoprazole drug, that is 2-[3-methyl-4-(2,2,2-trifluoroethane)-2-pyridyl)methyl]sulphonyl benzimidazole. Elemental analysis suggest that these metal ions forms ML_2Cl_2 stoichiometry for Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} and ML_2 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry for ZrO^{II} and VO^{II} . These complexes are non-electrolytic in nature. The ligand behaves as bidentate ON donor and forms coordinate bonds through C=N and S=O groups. Magnetic susceptibility, IR, UV-Visible and ESR spectral studies suggest that Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes posses octahedral geometry, whereas, ZrO^{II} and VO^{II} exhibit square pyramidal geometry. The ligand and its complexes were tested for their antimicrobial activity against *Klebsiella*, *Pseudomonas arginosa*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavous*.

Keywords : Lansoprazole, antimicrobial activity, electrical conductivity, transition metal complexes, ESR.

Introduction

The therapeutic activities of coordination compounds have been evaluated extensively^{1,2}. Some important examples of inorganic based drugs are metallocene antitumor complexes³, gold antiarthritic compounds⁴ and lithium antidepressants⁵. In all these cases, work is largely focused on elucidating the mechanism of action of these complexes. In principle, coordination compounds offer variety of geometries and reactivity. This is used in drug designing. Pt-DNA interaction has been stimulated by successful use of platinum complexes as a probe for the remarkable antitumor activity of certain platinum complexes⁴.

Metal complexes of semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones have aroused considerable interest in view of their industrial and biological importance. Many of these compounds possess a wide spectrum of medicinal properties⁴. The multifarious roles of transition metals in biochemistry⁶ suggests that considerable potential exists for the development of new chemistry with these metals in ligand system, specifically designed to serve these roles. Thiosemicarbazides and thiosemicarbazones form chelates with transition metal ions by bonding through the sulfur and nitrogen atom⁷. In view of these findings and in

continuation of our research work⁸, we are reporting the synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of 2-[3-methyl-4-(2,2,2-trifluoroethane)-2-pyridyl methyl sulphonyl benzimidazole (L) and its ZrO^{II} , VO^{II} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes in this communication.

Results and discussion

The analytical data of the complexes and their molar conductance values are given in Table 1. All these complexes are analyzed for 1 : 2 stoichiometry of the type ML_2Cl_2 and ML_2 . Measured conductance values of these complexes are too low to account for their electrolytic behavior.

IR spectra :

Complexes and their assignments are listed in Table 2 as per previous reports⁹⁻¹¹. The IR spectra of the complexes indicate that the ligand behaves as a neutral

Table 1. Elemental analysis, color, melting point and conductance data for ligand and metal complexes

Sl. no.	Ligand/Complex	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					M.p. (°C)	Color	Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
		C	H	N	M	Cl			
1.	L	52.23 (52.03)	37.59 (37.79)	11.29 (11.38)	–	–	163	Colorless	–
2.	VOL_2	45.30 (45.42)	3.04 (3.30)	9.50 (9.92)	12.50 (12.64)	–	250	Pale green	20.22
3.	ZrOL_2	47.46 (47.70)	3.38 (3.46)	10.52 (10.42)	12.5 (12.64)	–	190	Yellow	15.35
4.	MnL_2Cl_2	44.38 (44.56)	3.18 (3.24)	9.46 (9.74)	12.44 (12.74)	16.10 (16.20)	220	Pale pink	10.23
5.	FeL_2Cl_2	44.54 (44.44)	3.28 (3.24)	9.56 (9.72)	13.28 (12.92)	16.30 (16.20)	300	Red	16.13
6.	CoL_2Cl_2	44.18 (44.28)	3.12 (3.22)	9.28 (9.68)	13.68 (13.52)	16.43 (16.14)	280	Black	19.19
7.	NiL_2Cl_2	44.38 (44.30)	3.06 (3.24)	9.50 (9.68)	13.80 (13.54)	16.40 (16.14)	>300	Black	22.38
8.	CuL_2Cl_2	44.22 (44.04)	3.38 (3.20)	9.96 (9.62)	14.68 (14.52)	16.36 (16.08)	>300	Brown	18.98
9.	ZnL_2Cl_2	47.44 (47.78)	3.64 (3.48)	10.86 (10.50)	16.36 (16.26)	–	>300	Yellow	9.23
10.	CdL_2Cl_2	44.98 (44.50)	3.44 (3.28)	9.56 (9.86)	27.78 (26.42)	–	>300	Yellow	8.49
11.	HgL_2Cl_2	41.30 (40.90)	3.08 (2.98)	9.08 (8.94)	42.98 (42.74)	–	>300	Colorless	10.34

bidentate, and the metal coordinates via C=N and sulphonic acid groups (Fig. 1). The shift of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{S=O}}$ to lower wavelengths by 10–15 cm^{-1} in the complexes indicating that these groups are involved in the complexation. This band splits into two bands upon complexation, one appearing at frequency essentially the same as in the free ligand due to the presence of pyridine C=N, whereas the other at lower frequency¹². This indicates that only benzimidazole azomethine nitrogen coordinated to the central metal ion. $\nu_{\text{S=O}}$ ¹³ vibration occurs in the region 1459–1362 cm^{-1} have been assigned. The complexes display strong band due to M=O stretching frequencies in the region 985–952¹⁴ cm^{-1} . In addition to these bands, the vanadyl and zirconyl complexes exhibit the characteristics stretching frequencies for V=O and Zr=O asymmetric vibrations at 970 cm^{-1} and 989 cm^{-1} respectively. The bands appearing at 520, 440 and 285 cm^{-1} are attributed to M–O, M–N and M–Cl respectively¹⁵. In the complexes of $\nu_{\text{M–N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M–O}}$ vibrations occur in the region 540–490 cm^{-1} and 450–400 cm^{-1} respectively¹⁵. The weak to medium intensity bands observed in the complexes between 300–290 cm^{-1} and have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{M–Cl}}$ stretching frequency for the complexes as per previous assignments¹⁶.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of oxovanadium(II) complex displayed bands at 13888, 16666 and 21739 cm^{-1} assigned for $2B_2 \rightarrow 2E$, $2B_2 \rightarrow 2B_1$ and $2B_2 \rightarrow 2A_1$ transitions respectively. The electronic spectra of manganese(II) lansoprazole complex showed high intensity band around 27778 cm^{-1} . This has been assigned to the ligand metal charge transfer band. The remaining *d-d* bands are observed in the region 23809 and 17857 cm^{-1} ¹⁷. The iron(III) complexes have a tendency to possess high intensity charge transfer bands which makes the identification of *d-d* bands rather difficult. Iron(III) complex exhibit a very high intensity band around 23201 cm^{-1} due to ligand-metal charge transfer. This obscures the other *d-d* transition in visible region. It has been observed in the diffusion reflectance spectra that, iron(III) complex exhibit two bands in the 12500–10640 cm^{-1} and 20000–16670 cm^{-1} regions attributable to ${}^6A_1(G) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(G)$ and ${}^6A_1(G) \rightarrow {}^4A_1(G)$ transitions respectively¹⁸. Fe^{III} complex showed a weak and broad band maxima in the region 18518 cm^{-1} and 14326 cm^{-1} assigned to the ${}^6A_1(G) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(G)$ and ${}^6A_1(G) \rightarrow {}^4A_1(G)$ transitions respectively¹⁸.

Table 2. IR spectral data (cm⁻¹) of ligand and its complexes

Sl. no.	Ligand/Complexes	ν_{N-H}	$\nu_{C=N}$	$\nu_{S=O}$	ν_{C-N}	$\nu_{M=O}$	ν_{M-N}	ν_{M-O}	ν_{M-Cl}
1.	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SO ₂ F ₃	3230	1582	1414	1268	-	-	-	-
2.	VO(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SO ₂ F ₃) ₂	3240	1568	1418	1278	970	515	448	-
3.	ZrO(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SO ₂ F ₃) ₂	3231	1562	1362	1326	989	520	450	-
4.	Mn(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SO ₂ F ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	3222	1569	1437	1250	-	535	398	307
5.	Fe(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SO ₂ F ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	3236	1550	1481	1245	-	490	425	290
6.	Co(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SO ₂ F ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	3223	1566	1453	1262	-	508	429	300
7.	Ni(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SO ₂ F ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	3246	1553	1425	1289	-	496	426	305
8.	Cu(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SO ₂ F ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	3237	1559	1459	1263	-	495	438	309
9.	Zn(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SO ₂ F ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	3238	1562	1444	1268	-	510	450	295
10.	Cd(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SO ₂ F ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	3241	1558	1450	1268	-	520	449	307
11.	Hg(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ SO ₂ F ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	3235	1567	1428	1262	-	497	416	293

were M = Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}

were M = ZrO^{IV} and VO^{IV}

Fig. 1

The electronic spectra of cobalt(II) chelates showed two spin bands at 16666–17857 and 21739–22306 cm⁻¹, assignable to $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}(F)$ and $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. This conforms expected octahedral geometry for cobalt(II)¹⁹. The octahedral configuration of cobalt(II) complex is further confirmed by electron spectral transition observed at 16447 cm⁻¹ and 20833 cm⁻¹ and are assignable to $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}(F)$ and $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively.

The electronic spectra of nickel(II) complex exhibited two bands at 13513 and 23809 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to $^3A_{2g}(P) \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(F)$ and $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition respectively, suggesting an octahedral geometry²⁰ around Ni^{II}.

The broad bands observed in the electronic spectra of the copper(II) complex at 12820 cm⁻¹ assigned to $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2B_{2g}$, $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_{2g}$ transition are in analogy with expected tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry²¹. The broadness of the band may be due to dynamic and Jahn-Teller distortion.

Magnetic susceptibility data :

The magnetic moment obtained for the oxovanadium(II) complex at room temperature is 1.75 B. M. This is due to spin only value of oxovanadium(II) square pyramidal complex²².

The manganese(II) complex exhibit magnetic moment of 5.45 B.M. suggesting the formation of spin free complexes. This clearly agrees with the reported value of 5.90 B.M for manganese(II) complexes²³. The octahedral geometry of high spin iron(III) complexes are expected²⁴ to possess magnetic moment very close to spin only value of 5.92 B.M. The magnetic moment obtained for this complex is 5.83 B.M.

Table 3. ESR spectral data of drug complex

Sl. no.	Complex	$g_{ }$	g_e	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	G	α^2
1.	CuL ₂ Cl ₂	2.17	2.10	2.009	2.12	1.76	0.46

Table 4. Antimicrobial screening data of the ligand L and its complexes

Sl. no.	Compound/Complex	Antibacterial activity zone of inhibition (in mm)		Antifungal activity zone of inhibition (in mm)	
		<i>Klebsiclla</i>	<i>Pseudomonas</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavous</i>
	L	11.22	13.11	11.22	13.11
1.	ZrOL ₂	7.0	19.0	13.11	11.66
2.	VOL ₂	15.0	15.33	14.66	12.33
3.	FeL ₂ Cl ₂	17.33	15.44	12.66	13.33
4.	MnL ₂ Cl ₂	12.66	13.33	6.66	–
5.	CoL ₂ Cl ₂	–	14.33	–	14.33
6.	NiL ₂ Cl ₂	6.66	–	11.33	14.33
7.	CuL ₂ Cl ₂	11.33	14.33	17.33	15.44
8.	ZnL ₂	13.11	11.66	7.0	19.0
9.	CdL ₂	14.66	12.33	15.0	15.33
10.	HgL ₂	21.33	18.66	21.33	18.66
	Standard I (Gentamicine)	19.00	17.35	–	–
	Standard II (Grisofulvin)	–	–	20.11	21.33

The cobalt(II) complex shows magnetic moment of 4.65 B.M. The spin free octahedral complex of cobalt(II) is reported to exhibit magnetic moment in the range of 4.46 to 5.53 B.M.²⁵. Hence observed magnetic moment for the cobalt(II) complex indicates that it has an octahedral configuration.

The octahedral nickel(II) complexes are reported to exhibit magnetic moment in the range of 2.82 to 3.4 B.M.²⁶ including spin orbital coupling and contribution from ³A_{2g} and higher ³T_{2g} states. Hence, the observed magnetic moment value for the nickel(II) complex suggests that it may have octahedral geometry.

The copper(II) complex exhibit magnetic moment of 1.85 B.M. agreeable to spin only value. It is reported that the distorted octahedral geometry of copper(II) complex devoid of spin interaction exhibit magnetic moment is 1.80 B.M.²⁷. Hence, it may be concluded that copper(II) complex has major spin interaction.

ESR spectra :

The 'g' values obtained from the spectra are presented in Table 3. When the monomeric species change into dimeric species having axial symmetry and identical sites, the 'g' values also change due to the change in symmetry²⁸. From the observed 'g' values $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ (2.002), it is evident that the unpaired electron lies predominantly in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of copper(II) ion²⁹. The $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ (2.009) observed in the 'g' values suggests the presence of an

unpaired electron in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital. The values of the σ -bonding parameter, α^2 , show appreciable covalence character in the metal-ligand bond. Based on these observations copper(II) complex may have octahedral geometry.

Electrical conductivity :

The temperature dependence of the conductivity of the compressed pellet of the cobalt(II) complex has been determined in the temperature 428–478 K. Its conductivity is 10^{-12} – 10^{-9} S cm⁻¹ with band gap of 0.1433 eV. At room temperature it behaves as electrical insulator. In general, the lower conductivity of the complex may be attributed to the effective packing of the non-planar bulky molecule.

The Arrhenous plot (Fig. 2) clearly indicates the effect of complexation. The electrical conductivity of the complexes increases with increasing temperature. At room temperature complexes behave as an insulator but at higher temperature, that exhibit semi conducting nature. This may be due to the overlap of the anti bonding π -orbitals of the σ donor ligand (lansoprazole), to the empty d -orbitals of the different transition metal cations. It leads to delocalization of the π -electronic charges on the ligand.

Antimicrobial activity :

Antimicrobial activity of ligand and their metal complexes are given in Table 4. These data reveals that the antimicrobial activity could be mainly due to the

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of Electrical conductivity of the complex.

structure of the complexes and also the oxidation state of the metal ions. Better activities of some of the metal complexes as compared to the ligand can be explained by chelation theory. The theory explains that decrease in polarizability of the metal could enhance the lipophilicity of the complexes which leads to the breakdown of permeability of the cells resulting in interference with normal cell process³⁰.

Antibacterial activity of the ligand and complexes reveal that, the activity zone of inhibition for all the complexes except ZrO^{II} complexes with 7 mm and for Ni^{II} complexes with 6 mm, which is higher than with 11 to 21 mm zone of inhibition, whereas ligand showed only 11.22 mm inhibition. Mercury complex of this ligand showed higher activity with 21 mm inhibition whereas the standard drug Gentamicine showed 19.00 mm inhibition at the same concentration as of the test drug.

The antibacterial activity of all the complexes against *Pseudomonas* except Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes with 11 and 12 mm inhibition respectively, showed higher activity with 13–19 mm inhibition against *Pseudomonas*. Standard drug Gentamicine showed only 17 mm inhibition at the same concentration.

Antifungal activity studies of ligand and its metal complexes in the present study against *A. niger* showed that except Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with 6.66 mm and 7.00 mm inhibition respectively showed higher activity with 11 and 21 inhibition than the ligand which showed

11.22 mm inhibition, Hg^{II} complex showed higher activity than standard Grisofulvin which showed 20.11 mm inhibition against the same organism at the same concentration as that of the test drug.

Antifungal activity studies of ligand and its complexes against *A. flavous* of the present study showed that all the complexes except ZrO^{II} and VO^{II} complexes with 11.66 mm and 12.33 mm inhibition respectively showed higher activity with 12 to 19 mm inhibition when compared to that of ligand which showed only 13.11 mm inhibition at the same concentration as that of the test drug. However, ligand and their complexes showed lower activity when compared to standard drug Grisofulvin with 21.33 mm inhibition at the same concentration.

Experimental

Analytical grade metal chloride salts, viz. NiCl_2 , CoCl_2 , MnCl_2 , CuCl_2 , FeCl_3 , ZrOCl_2 , ZnCl_2 , CdCl_2 and HgCl_2 of Lancaster and Lobachemie were used without any purification and lansoprazole drug procured from Sigma-Aldrich and recrystallised from the distilled alcohol⁸.

Conductivity measurements were made using an Elico CM-82 Conductivity Bridge. Electronic spectra of the complexes were taken in DMSO on Systronic spectrophotometer in the range of 200–900 nm. The magnetic susceptibility were measured at room temperature using the Gouy balance. IR spectra of the ligands and complexes were recorded in KBr matrix using Perkin-Elmer 1000 FTIR spectrometer in the range of 4000–250 cm^{-1} . The electron spin resonance spectra of Cu^{II} complexes in poly crystalline state were recorded on Varian X-band ESR spectrometer using diphenyl picryl hydrazine (DPPH) as a reference standard free radical.

The electronic spectra were recorded on a Varian-Cary/2390 spectrophotometer at RSIC, IIT, Madras. Electrical conductivity of solid complexes were measured using digital micro voltmeter model DMV-001 with DC method over wide temperature ranges. Nitrogen was determined by the Dumas method and sulfur was estimated by the Messenger's method. The bio-efficacies of the synthesized compounds were tested *in vitro* and *in vivo*. *In vitro* tests were conducted for growth inhibitory activity against the common microorganisms viz. *Klebsiella*, *Pseudomonas arginosa*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavous*. The radial growth and the disc methods¹⁸ were employed to evaluate fungicidal and bactericidal activities, respectively.

Preparation of oxo-vanadyl chloride :

V₂O₅ (0.455 g, 2.5 mM) was reacted with 5 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid in presence of a few drops of ethanol on a water bath until all the V₂O₅ dissolved to form a blue colored oxovanadyl chloride solution.

Preparation of metal(II) complexes :

Metal chlorides (0.01 mol) in ethanol was added in an ethanolic solution of ligand (0.02 mol). The reaction mixture was heated and refluxed for about one hour in presence of few drops of concentrated HCl. On cooling, the complex separated, was filtered and washed several times with alcohol and dried *in vacuo* over phosphorus pentoxide.

Conclusion :

We propose the octahedral structure for Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}, square pyramidal geometry for ZrO^{II} and VO^{II} complexes. The DC electrical conductivity data reveals that these complexes act as insulators at room temperature, however as temperature increases the conductivity increases indicating a semi conducting behaviour.

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